

dichloride (25 ml) at 0–5° and the mixture was stirred for 10–15 min at that temperature. The imine (3; 10 mmol) was then added to it followed by dropwise addition of triethylamine (4.2 ml, 30 mmol) in methylene dichloride (15 ml). The resulting mixture was stirred overnight (20–24 h) at room temperature and then washed with water (100 ml). The organic layer was separated, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated to give an oil which on treatment with ethanol yielded the β -lactams (4–11).

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Synthesis of a Dehydroretinol Congener

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3-Ethoxyanhydroretinol (4) is formed in high yield when 3-dehydroretinol (1) is treated with ethanolic hydrogen chloride^{1–4}. Variation of reaction conditions resulted in the formation of a number of compounds, one which viz. 3-ethoxyretroretinyl ethyl ether has already been described⁵. Here we report the synthesis of another 3-dehydroretinol congener, viz. 3-ethoxyretinyl ethyl ether (7) by the treatment of compound 1 with ethanolic hydrogen chloride (0.13 N) for 1.5 h.

The minced liver of *Bagarius bagarius* was extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°) as usual⁶. The reddish brown liver oil (2 g) so obtained ($\epsilon_{1\text{ cm}}^{1\%}$ at 345 nm = 144.6) dissolved in light petroleum (5 ml) was chromatographed on water-deactivated alumina column (5%, v/w). The dehydroretinyl ester (0.2365 g, $\epsilon_{1\text{ cm}}^{1\%}$ at 351 nm = 520) was collected and saponified with 10% (w/v) ethanolic KOH (100 ml) at 50–60° for 40 min. The unsaponifiable matter was extracted with light petroleum, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting 3-dehydroretinol was

treated with dry ethanolic hydrogen chloride (0.13 N; 100 ml) and allowed to stand in dark at room temperature (30°) for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted with light petroleum. The extract was washed, dried and finally concentrated to about 5 ml and chromatographed on water-deactivated alumina (5%, v/w). The fourth greenish-yellow zone was eluted with light petroleum containing 5% diethyl ether. On repeated chromatography, the single zone separated into two distinct yellow zones. The eluate was then collected and fractions having similar uv spectra were pooled together. The fraction was characterised as 3-ethoxyretroretinyl ethyl ether⁵. The second zone was also collected in fractions by elution with light petroleum containing 6% diethyl ether. Fractions having similar uv spectra were pooled together and rechromatographed for further purification. The purified compound (2.5 mg) showed a single spot on a silica gel plate (0.25 mm thick) with a solvent system of acetone–light petroleum (1 : 19, v/v), R_f = 0.48.

On the basis of chemical analysis and spectral evidences, structure 7 was assigned to the product, λ_{max} 328 (light petroleum) and 330 nm (ethanol); the SbCl_5 reaction gave λ_{max} 670 nm; ν_{max} 2965, 2925, 2860, 1450, 1375, 1275, 1105 and 965 cm^{-1} ; δ (60 MHz; CCl_4) 1.0–1.6 (14H, m, 4- CH_2 and ring methylene protons at C-2), 1.7 (3H, s, ring allylic CH_3 at C-5), 1.9 (6H, s, 2- CH_3 in acyclic

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